

DANCING ANGLES: MAKING SENSE OF ANGLES THROUGH MATERIALLY GROUNDED ENACTIVE METAPHORS

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This study explores primary students' metaphorical mapping, under the lens of enactive and new materialist perspectives, paying closer attention on their interactions with the material world. It focuses on the kind of metaphors and meanings for angles that emerge through materially grounded enactments, during an activity based on dance. In the context of the design-based research methodology, seven 9-year-old students used a digital tool that enabled collaborative embodied interaction along with physical manipulatives, to create digital animations simulating dance movements. The paper presents preliminary findings from the thematic analysis of audio, screen, and video recordings, in the form of critical episodes, illustrating how students' metaphors and meanings of angles as variable quantities emerged as enactive as well as materially grounded.

Keywords: angle, enactive metaphors, embodied interaction, manipulatives, dance

INTRODUCTION

The concept of angle has long been central to mathematics education (Mitchelmore & White, 2000). Traditionally, research on learning about angles has focused on models of progressive geometric comprehension (see for example Mitchelmore & White, 2000). Although these approaches recognize the role of embodied experience and the material world in mathematical learning, they often treat these aspects as a starting point rather than as central to sense making. In the context of recent approaches, physical actions, such as body movements, and manipulation of tangible or digital objects, play a central role on mathematical learning (Núñez & Lakoff, 2005; de Freitas & Sinclair, 2013). Following this line, in this study, we examine the kind of conceptual metaphors (Nunez & Lakoff, 2005) and meanings about angles, primary students express when they use a digital tool which allows embodied interaction, in combination with physical manipulatives, to create animations simulating dance movements. Previous studies have also examined the potential of linking dance and mathematics to achieve mathematical learning (Gerofsky, 2013). For example Karavakou & Kynigos (2024) concluded that the aesthetically driven aspect of the tasks related to dance supported various supported 11th grade students' thinking on periodic covariation. In a similar line, Watson (2005) discusses in her study how kinaesthetic experiences associated with dance promoted learning about spatial and symbolic aspects of mathematics.

Under the lens of enactive (Varela et a.,2017) and new materialistic approaches (de Freitas & Sinclair, 2013), we aim to reframe the process of metaphorical mapping, paying closer attention on how it emerges through students' interactions with the material world. In the context of the design-based (DBR) research methodology (Bakker, 2018), we designed and implemented an educational activity in real classroom settings, during which we collected audio, video and screen recording data. The data analysis was based on two research questions (RQ): What kind of metaphors (RQ1) and what kind of meanings (RQ2) regarding the concept of angle emerge when students use an embodied interaction digital tool in combination with physical manipulatives?

METAPHORS: FOUNDATIONS AND NEW PERSPECTIVES

According to embodied cognition theorists, individuals conceptualise abstract concepts, such as the mathematical concept of angle, through the use of embodied metaphors (Núñez & Lakoff, 2005). A metaphor is an implicit analogy in which a comparison is made between two experiential domains (Presmeg, 2013), a process described as *cross-domain* or *metaphorical mapping*. An example of an embodied metaphor is the body-syntonicity metaphor (Papert, 1980), where the individual synchronises their own body with the body of an entity or an object so that they understand its behaviour. Bridging the ideas of embodied cognition with the notion of enactment (Varela et al., 2017), Gallagher and Lindgren (2015) take one step further and introduce the term *enactive metaphors*. Enactive metaphors are brought into existence not only through bodily engagement but also through purposeful action (Gallagher & Lindgren, 2015). Focusing on enactive metaphors, in our study, we employ dance as a metaphorical domain for making sense of angles. In this context, angle is approached as a dynamic turn, which requires intentional, coordinated movement through space.

Although Núñez and Lakoff (2005) emphasize the embodied aspects of metaphors, metaphorical mapping is typically described as a solely mental process expressed through language (Presmeg, 2013), often treated as independent of the material world (Sinclair & Schiralli, 2003). In this study, we emphasise the role of students' bodily interactions with the material environment (de Freitas & Sinclair, 2013) on the kind of conceptual metaphors they formulate, focusing on the combined use of an embodied interaction digital tool and the use of physical manipulatives. Within conceptual metaphor theory (Nunez & Lakoff, 2005), manipulatives as well as digital artefacts can be seen as providing concrete source domains that support metaphorical mapping. Taking a new materialistic perspective (de Freitas & Sinclair, 2013) this study considers these elements as parts of body-matter assemblages through which enactive metaphors emerge as vehicles for meaning making (de Freitas & Sinclair, 2013). Accordingly, metaphorical mapping is approached as a material discursive practice (de Freitas & Sinclair, 2013) rather than a mental process that is expressed through metaphorical language.

METHODS AND TOOLS

The study adopts a qualitative design-based research (DBR) methodology, including the design of tools and activities and their implementation in real school settings (Bakker, 2018). DBR is conducted in repetitive cycles of design, implementation, and evaluation, where the evaluation of each cycle informs the re-design and implementation of the following cycle (Bakker, 2018). The aim in DBR is not generalisation; but the development of insights and design principles that can inform educational theory as well as educational practice (Bakker, 2018). In this paper we present the results from the analysis of the first cycle of implementation. During the activities, seven fourth-grade students from a primary school used a digital tool that allowed embodied interaction, in combination with pipe cleaners, to create digital animations that simulated dance movements. The intervention lasted five hours and it was implemented in the context of the formal school schedule in collaboration with the classroom teacher. Students worked in pairs of 2-3. Each group used one computer and one pair of headphones. Students used two microworlds that were designed in the MaLT2Dance digital environment (<https://extendt2.com/widgets/malt2dance/>), an extension of MaLT2 with motion capturing technology. In these microworlds, children used two sliders (Figure 1a) to transform the shapes displayed on the screen, in order to make them "dance" according to

the music they had selected. Students could move the sliders either using the mouse or through their hands' movements which were captured by the digital environment (Figure 2e). Along with the transformation of the shape on the digital scene, by adjusting the sliders, the corresponding numerical values beneath, indicated the measure of the angle being changed (Figure 1b). In the first microworld, slider (x) adjusts the measure of the red angle, while slider (y) adjusts the measure of the blue angle (Figure 1b).

Fig1. In the first microworld, students could move two sliders (a). Increasing the value of the slider (x) causes the red angle to “open” toward the bottom of the screen, while increasing the value of the slider (y) causes the blue angle to “open” toward the top of the screen (b)

In the second microworld, one slider (x) adjusted the measure of both angles displayed on the screen (Figures 2a, b), while the second slider (a) controlled the angular transformation that determined their orientation (Figures 2c, d).

Fig2. The second microworld: moving slider (a) changes the measure of the angles (a, b), while moving slider (x) changes the direction of the angles (c, d)

Audio, video and screen recordings were collected and analysed based on the thematic analysis approach (Xu & Zammit, 2020), following four steps: (1) synchronization and transcription; (2) identification of critical episodes involving metaphor or meaning-making; (3) thematic coding of these incidents using terms from related literature (e.g., "angle as a measure", "body syntonicity metaphor") and (4) categorization into themes based on metaphor types and emergent meanings. The next section presents indicative episodes, of body-syntonic and spatial metaphors and students' sense making of angles as variable quantities.

RESULTS

Body syntonic and spatial metaphors

The context of dance afforded students an initial framing of angular transformations through movement-based concepts rooted in their embodied experience. They used body-syntonicity metaphors (e.g. the splits to describe the straight angle), where the individual identifies their body with an object, using it as a reference point for making sense of its behavior (Papert, 1980). Specifically they associated the shapes on the digital screen with dancers' bodies or body parts. In the following excerpt, the student (S4) describes to the researcher (R) the sequence of movements in the choreography she has prepared with her classmate manipulating the sliders with her hands.

- S4: To make the splits, you have to move it all the way to 180 (Figure 3a). Then straight forward, 90 (Figure 3b). And then a pirouette, we turn (Figure 3c), we make it do a circle, I need to go all the way to the end and then all the way again (she moves the slider bar to 180 and then back to -180).

Fig3. The student moves the slider to the values at which the angles represent the dance figure she describes each time

The student in this case uses the body syntonicity metaphor to communicate the shape's movements as a result of changing the values of the sliders. Angle measures (e.g., 180°) are connected to intentional actions (Gallagher & Lindgren, 2015) and expressed through metaphorical language (Presmeg, 2013). For example, the use of the "split" is linked with the expression "all the way" and the value "180" to describe a straight angle.

In line with previous studies on metaphorical mapping, students also used the spatial metaphor (Pit & Casasando, 2022) to refer to angular changes, a metaphor which is inherently informed by the material physical space and the way their bodies were moving in it. In the following episode, one of the students uses the mouse and the other one his hand to make the shapes „dance“ in the first microworld (Figure 1a, b). Their goal is to synchronize their actions so that the angles form a figure in which the moving sides approach and move away from each other, according to the song rhythm. The student (S5) controlling the slider for the blue angle (y) guides their peer (S6), who adjusts the red angle by moving the slider (x) with their hand. While the second student tries to open the red angle symmetrically (Figure 5a), S5 makes an observation:

Fig4. (a) The slider shows the value -7. (b) The student observes that the slider value is 30, saying "it's not negative"

- S5: It needs to go forward (referring to the red line segment shown at the bottom of the screen, he means it should move toward the top of the screen, he means it should move toward the top of the screen, it's not minus (Figure 4a).
- S6: But, when it goes this way (he moves his hand in a way that increases the value of slider (x), and the line segment moves lower on the screen, as shown in Figure 4b), it's not minus... (the slider value is 30).
- S5: Wait, follow me (S5 activates the second hand... Up-down, up-down (Figure 5a, b).
- S6: No, no, it's in and out, in and out. In, comes closer like this (Figure 5c), and then *out*, it moves farther away (Figure 5d).

Fig5. (a, b) S5 suggests that they move their hands "up" and "down". (c, d) S6 observes that the movement they need to perform should be "in" (c) and "out" (d) so that the shape changes symmetrically

In this episode, the movement toward "forward" is associated with an increase in the slider's value, while "in" and "out", although not explicitly stated, are aligned with being close to or far from the value 0 on the two sliders but also from one another. In the episode students made sense of the empty space between their hands (Abrahamson & Sánchez-García, 2016) and used it in reference to their bodies to describe the movement they had to do.

Angles as variable quantities

In the beginning of the activity, when asked what was the result of moving the sliders, students argued that the sliders "change the angle". However, they pointed to the moving line segment,

revealing their confusion regarding the relationship of the angle size with its side lengths (Psycharis & Kynigos, 2008). As the students aimed to create dance figures and choreographies, their attention gradually shifted from the visual elements of the shape to focusing on the process of its transformation through the movement of the sliders. In the next episode, when the researcher asked the children what does the first slider move, S7 explained:

S7: It makes it bigger and then smaller.

R: What becomes bigger and then smaller?

S7: The red one, when it opens it goes to a bigger number. For example, here it starts at zero (Figure 6a) and I go to 45 and it opens (Figure 6b).

Fig6. The student moves the slider to show how “the red one becomes bigger” when she moves the slider from the value 0 (a) to the value 45”

S8: No this is the same (showing the red part of the pipe cleaner), we did not use another one...

S7: The angle! The angle is this thing, which is like this, when it is right (Figure 7a). I move this and I make it smaller (Figure 7b).

Fig7. The student shows the right angle (a) and how she makes it smaller (b). She points to the space between the pipecleaners to show what changes (c)

R: What becomes smaller?

S7: This...(shows the space between the red and the blue parts of the pipecleaner as shown in Figure 7c)

In this episode, the concept of angle is explored in reference to its degrees. The students attempt to identify exactly what changes each time they move the sliders. While initially angles were sensed as the line segments, S7 finally relates the arithmetic values that change with the slider to the empty space between the parts of the pipecleaner, the lines of the angle. Here, the student makes sense of the angle as a variable quantity as she senses the physical change in the manipulative.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUDING REMARKS

This study examined the types of conceptual metaphors (Núñez & Lakoff, 2005) and the meanings that emerged among primary students during an activity that combined the use of and embodied interaction digital tool with the use of physical manipulatives to create animations simulating dance movements. Students used bodysyntonic and spatial metaphors to refer to angles as dynamic movements. They associated these movements with symbolic values, making sense of angles as variable quantities. In the context of dance, students' metaphors and meanings emerged through materially grounded enactments rather through a mere mental comparative cognitive process, as scholars in embodied cognition have described (Nunez & Lakoff, 2005). On one hand the embodied interaction with the digital tool allowed students to use the empty space between their hands to ground and describe their actions (Abrahamson & Sánchez-García, 2016). On the other hand, in line with previous studies (Latsi & Kynigos, 2022) manipulatives were not merely supports for mental metaphorical mapping, but active participants, as their constraints and affordances (bending, holding shape etc.) made angular transformations tangible, allowing students to enact the variability of angles.

In our study, students were able to move beyond focusing solely on the visible elements of angles, describing angles as the space between two line segments. This way of perceiving angles has also been documented in earlier research (Mitchelmore & White, 2000). According to Clements and Battista (1989), viewing an angle merely as "space" neglects its dynamic aspect. However, in this study, students did not treat the space statically; instead, they conceived it dynamically, using the pipe-cleaner model to demonstrate how this "space" changes when manipulated. Nevertheless, conceptualizing angles in this way may also give rise to misconceptions. For instance, students might later find it difficult to understand straight or zero angles or distinguish the concept of angle and that of area and its measurement. Further research is needed to examine how the idea of angle as "space" may influence students' understanding. Even though, this study has important limitations regarding the small size and duration, these preliminary insights, show that employing enactive and materialistic approaches on studying metaphorical mapping, can open new directions in studying this process as a material-discursive practice (de Freitas & Sinclair, 2013).

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